

Factors Affecting Awareness of Community Driven Development Projects in Himachal Pradesh : A Comparison of of HP Mid-Himlayan Watershed Development Project and Swachh Bharat Mission

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Introduction : From modernisation in the post-War era to the present concept of development as sustenance, self-esteem and freedom (Todaro & Smith, 2003), the concept of development has undergone a lot of change. Development programmes having horizontal outreach, dialogue, access and also participation of the community, both in decision making and implementation, have been found to have better success rates. Various approaches, such as ‘another development,’ ‘alternate development,’ ‘participatory development,’ and ‘empowerment’ (Mefalopoulos, 2003), evolved and experimented over the years bear a testimony to the recognition the role of the community in development.

Community Driven Development (CDD) is a more recent derivate of Community-based development (CBD) approach. Together, as per Mansuri and Rao (2004), they are “among the fastest growing mechanisms for channeling development assistance” (2004, p. 2).

India’s community-led development approach had its roots in lessons learnt from the country’s struggle for independence and was influenced by Mahatma Gandhi. Experience with Mahatma Gandhi’s *Sarvodaya* movement and *Gram Swaraj*, and Vinoba Bhave’s *Bhoodan* movement of 1951, inspired the evolution of Indian community development initiatives under the first and the second Five Year Plans (Oommen, 1984). Since the highpoint of the LCDD, which Binswanger-Mkhize, et al (2010) trace back to 1950s in India, has empowered the communities to devise their own development plans, adopt best practices for execution and monitoring and finally share the benefits equitably.

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In the 7th Five Year Plan (1985-90), public participation in development and decentralisation were made a top priorities (Kurien, 1992). From the constitutional prospective, the concept of democratic decentralisation received a much need boost through 73rd and 74th Constitutional Amendments which institutionalised the role of Panchayati Raj Institutions (PRIs) and local self-governance in the early 1990s (Binswanger-Mkhize, et al., 2010). Several developmental programmes since then such as Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme (MNERGS), Total Sanitation Programme (TSC)/ Swachh Bharat Mission (SBM) at the national level, and Himachal Pradesh Mid Himalayan Watershed Development Project (HPMHWD) at the state level, have been initiated with the community at the center of planning and implementation.

Now rechristened as Swachh Bharat Mission, started on October 2, 2014, Total Sanitation Campaign, is an Indian government initiative aimed to eradicate Open Defecation in India by October 2019, and bring a change in the mindset of the community towards cleanliness practices. The programme gives emphasis on creating awareness through intensive use of IEC strategies to bring about attitudinal and behavioural changes for universal hygiene practices. The HPMHWDP was a multi-sectoral project covering a total of 710 gram panchayats and 2.71 lakh households. The projects aimed to reverse degradation of the natural resources, improve the productivity potential of all renewable natural resources, and raise the income of the rural households using the CDD approach.

Aim, Objectives and Need for the Study

The aim of the study is to evaluate awareness and the factors that affect awareness of the stakeholders in CDD projects.

The following objectives were decided for the study:

- To determine the most effective outreach sources for Community Driven Development projects.
- To explore the differences between HPMHWDP and TSC/SBM in the level of awareness of stakeholders
- To explore socio-economic variables that affect awareness about CDD projects.

The present research study on evaluation of awareness dimension of outreach is a small part of an ongoing study of outreach components of CDD projects through an evaluation of awareness and participation of the community. Such a study has the potential of not only improving the outcomes and impacts of CDD projects,

especially in Himachal Pradesh, but also of the future CDD projects in the country and other parts of the world.

Review of Literature

Community Driven Development – The Indian Context: At the heart of an ideal understanding of Community Development lies the dynamism in the way the members of the community share common resources and benefits equitably (Chekki, 1979). Community development is fundamentally, more or less, a well defined process useful to broaden the involvement, participation and political foothold from initiation to outcome of the programmes.

Citizens' participation in the development holds immense importance in promoting social understanding, strengthening of democratic values and removing inequalities (Dreze & Sen, 2002). Development economists have also found "development participation" as useful tool for encouraging the civil society to take up the ownership of development projects. Multilateral funding agencies like World Bank made a policy decision to include community participation as key element of the projects.

Community Development and Communication: Communication is believed to be the backbone of all development effort, especially in case of development programmes involving community participation. The new paradigm in the development communication came with Rogers (1976) who stressed upon taking into account the communication effects gap and the limitations of the social structure on developmental communication effects. He proposed a better focus on content of mass media messages about development. Noar, Harrington, & Aldrich (2009) divided the communication into three generic forms – personalized generic communication, targeted communication and tailored communication. Singhal, Njogu, Bouman, & Elías (2006) assert that entertainment-education has been effective as a communication tool for reaching out to the masses and developing social capital in the communities. Community development projects have relied extensively on various theories and model of behaviour change such as theory of planned behaviour, health belief model, social learning theory, theory of reasoned action, etc. Even as the theory of reasoned action (TRA) and its modified version, the theory of planned behaviour (TPB), referred to together as theory of reasoned action/planned behaviour which link beliefs and behaviour, were used extensively to guide behaviour change components of community development programmes (Ajzen, 1991). Bandura (1986, 2008), building upon the insights gained from years

of research on social learning theory, incorporated the influence of social interactions, experiences, and outside media influences on behaviour change in his social cognitive theory (SCT).

Research Design : A mixed-method research design was developed for this study using both quantitative methodologies and primary data collected through a survey using a questionnaire. Both Data was analysed using descriptive statistics with IBM SPSS 20.0. Himachal Pradesh has a total of 12 districts. TSC/SBM, being a national programme is operational in all twelve districts of the state. HPMHWDP was undertaken in 10 of the twelve districts – all districts except the tribal districts of Kinnaur, and Lahaul and Spiti. The survey for each study was conducted in 50% of the project districts. The sample was collected from 50% of the districts covered under each project. Thus, for the evaluation of TSC/SBM, six districts, selected randomly were Hamirpur, Kangra, Kullu, Sirmour, Solan and Una. For HPMHWDP, the five districts, selected out of ten were Bilaspur, Chamba, Kangra, Sirmour and Solan. One gram panchayat from each of the selected districts was selected randomly for data collection. All the residents of rural areas in the project districts, 18 years of age or above, were considered as the population for the study, with all such individuals as the sample unit. Multistage sampling was used to reach a total sample size of 618 for the study. Expecting high sample mortality, 400 sample units were targeted, resulting in a final sample of 265 for the TSC/SBM survey and 353 for HPMHWDP study, leading to a total sample size of 618. Cross-tabulations and missing case analysis revealed 617 valid cases.

The following research questions were framed:

1. What are the most significant sources of awareness for the people about both the projects, TSC/SBM and HPMWWDP?
2. What is the level of awareness generated by the project outreach in the stakeholders of both the projects, TSC/SBM and HPMWWDP?
3. What are the socio-economic variables that affect awareness about CDD projects?

Results and Discussion : Of the 265 respondents for TSC/SBM study, more than half (52.1%, N = 138) were from Solan district. Respondents from Una and Hamirpur constitute 13.6% (N = 36) and 10.9% (N = 29) of the sample, respectively. Respondents from Kangra (9.1%, N = 24), Kullu (8.7%, N = 23) and Sirmour (5.7%, N = 15) districts constitute for less than ten percent of the sample each. Also, 55.5% (N = 147) were males and 44.5% (N = 118) were

females. In case of HPMHWDP, of the 353 respondents, 61.8% (N = 218) were from Solan district. Respondents from Chamba and Sirmaur (N = 35 each) constituted 9.9% respectively of the sample. Respondents from Bilaspur (9.3%, N = 33) and Kangra (91.1%, N = 32) were less than ten percent of the sample each. Of these, 59.8% (N = 211) were males and 40.2% (N = 142) were females. Sample distribution for other socio-economic variables are not discussed in favour of brevity.

To answer research question no.1, "What are the most significant sources of awareness for the people about both the projects, TSC/SBM and HPMWDP?", respondents were sought on three dimensions. The respondents were asked to choose the one medium from a list the medium which was provided introductory project information; detailed information; and which was considered the most effective source of project information.

The source of primary awareness both the projects differed quite a lot. For MHWDP the significant sources were informal meetings (78.5%), and traditional media like newspapers, television, radio etc. (15.1%). In case of TSC/SBM, the significant sources were traditional media (54%) and informal meetings (24.5%). In fact for both the projects combined, each of the other sources (outdoor ads, street plays/folk media, public lectures/talks, formal community gatherings, and informal inter-personal interactions) accounts for introductory information to less than four percent of the respondents. Chi-square test reveals a significant difference between the various sources being the source of introductory information to MHWDP and TSC/SBM, $\chi^2(7, N = 596) = 198.49, p = .00$.

Informal meetings and media were observed as important source of detailed information about development projects for a fairly large proportion of respondents (55.8% and 19.9% respectively). Other significant sources included formal gathering (6.8%), street plays /folk media (6.3%), outdoor ads (5.0%), public lectures /talks (3.4%) and informal interpersonal gathering (1.3%). However a comparison of MHWDP and TSC/SMB reveals a significant difference in proportion of the respondents reporting various media and other sources of detailed information. Out of 352 respondents, 70.5 percent reported informal meeting as detailed source of information and 11.9% reported formal community gathering as detailed sources of information in case of MHWDP project. Only 3.7 percent reported media and outdoor meeting as source of detailed information. For the TSC/SBM project, 265 respondents, 41.5%

reported media as source of details information while informal meetings were detailed source of information for 36.2 percent respondents Other important source of information were street plays and formal media (11.3%), public ads (6.8%) and public lectures/talks (2.6%). Therefore, we observed by the chi-square tests that there is significant difference between both projects MHWDP and TSC/SBM about source of detailed information. $\chi^2 (7, N = 618) = 199, p = .00$.

Effective source of information for the above projects was quite different. In case of MHWDP, a large proportion (73.7%) of respondents considered Informal meetings as an effective source of information whereas for TSC/SBM, Media was considered an effective source of information by 48.7% respondents. The second most effective source of information for MHWDP was street plays/folk media (15.0%). For TSC/SMB project Informal meetings was considered effective by 32.5%. Two other two sources of information were public lectures/talks (3.4%) and outdoor ads (3.1%) respectively for the MHWDP project. But in case of TSC/SBM, Outdoor ads were considered effective by 7.9% and Street plays/Folk media by same 7.2% respondents. Overall, for both the projects combined, meetings (56%) and media (21.8%) were considered effective source of information. The chi-square test revealed a significant difference for various sources of effective information about the MHWDP and TSC/SBM projects. $\chi^2 (7, N = 618) = 219.48, p = .00$

To find answer to research question, "What is the level of awareness generated by the project outreach in the stakeholders of both the projects, TSC/SBM and HPMWWDP," the respondents were asked to rate their own perceived level of awareness on a three-point Likert-type scale. That has detailed reflection in the data distribution .

A very high proportion (85.8%, N = 303) MHWDP respondents out of 353 were completely aware of the project, while around three-fourth of the 265 TSC/SBM respondents (73.6%, N = 195) were completely aware. While a very few (5.1%, N = 18) MWDP were found completely unaware, this proportion was relatively higher for TSC/SBM (16.2%, N = 43). The Chi-square test revealed highly significant difference in the proportion of the respective MHWDP and TSC/SBM respondents having different levels of awareness, $\chi^2 (2, N = 618) = 22.007, p = .00$.

Thus, it may be concluded that the average level of awareness is much higher amongst MHWDP as compared to

TSC/SBM. It is clear that awareness about both the projects was extremely high amongst the community members. However, the level of awareness was higher in case of HPMHWDP as compared to TSC/SBM.

To help answer the Research Question 3, “What are the socio-economic variables that affect awareness about CDD projects,” the level of awareness of the combined sample from both the projects was cross-tabulated with sex, age, education, economic status, caste, and occupation.

Of the 288 male respondents 46.5% (N = 134) were unaware of the projects while of the 329 female respondents 64.4% (N = 212) were unaware of the projects. Similarly, there was a big difference in the proportion of male and female respondents (41.3% and 28.3% respectively) who were completely aware of the project. Difference was also observed in the proportion of male (12.2%, N = 35) and female (7.3%, N = 24) respondents who were partially aware. Male respondents reported better awareness levels than female respondents. The Chi-Square test revealed a significant difference in the level of awareness between both sexes, $\chi^2(2, N = 617) = 20.19, p = .00$.

There was a big difference of 25 percentage points between the most unaware education group, high-school educated (61.8%) and the least unaware group of post-graduates (36.8%). Alternatively, it can be explained that though the proportion of respondents who reported partial awareness ranged from 8.5% to 11.4% across all education groups, combined with “completely aware” responses, the respondents with high-school education were the least aware while the average level of awareness was the highest in respondents with post-graduate education. The Chi-Square test reveals a very significant difference in the levels of awareness about the projects in different age groups, $\chi^2(6, N = 617) = 22.35, p = .01$.

The level of awareness about project awareness was higher amongst below poverty line respondents with only 47.8% (N = 98) being completely unaware as compared to 70.2% (N = 248) poverty line respondents being completely unaware. The Chi-Square test revealed a significant difference in the level of awareness between respondents of the two economic status, $\chi^2(2, N = 617) = 8.53, p = .04$.

The levels of unawareness seemed to have a direct link of the type of occupation. The unemployed, who have the time or the highest potential of benefitting from the projects have the highest levels of unawareness, with only 9.8% (N = 5) while 76.5% (N = 39) reported being completely aware. The levels of awareness seem to

rise with the leisure and social capital afforded by the respective employment with levels of awareness being the highest for salaried (39.4%, N = 13 unaware), self-employed (41.5%, N = 17 unaware), agriculturists/horticulturist (63.1%, N = 303 unaware) and daily wagers (66.7%, N = 8 unaware). The Chi-square test revealed a highly significant difference in the level of awareness across respondents of different occupation groups, $\chi^2(8, N = 617) = 116.85$, $p = .00$.

Research Question 3 was, “What socio-demographic factors are responsible for different levels of awareness about the projects?” It has been found that sex, level of education, economic status and occupation corresponded significantly with level of awareness about the CDD projects (HPMHWDP and TSC/SBM combined). As expected, males were better aware than females; and BPL respondents were better aware than APL. Respondents engaged in agriculture/horticulture, self-employed or daily wagers, were less aware about the projects as compared to salaried or unemployed people.

Conclusions : This research study set out to evaluate and compare the awareness dimension of outreach of Community-Driven Development projects in Himachal Pradesh – large-scale, national-level, Total Sanitation Campaign (later, renamed Swachh Bharat Mission – TSC/SBM), and another, smaller in scale, state-level project Himachal Pradesh Mid-Himalayan Watershed Development Project (HPMHWDP). Earlier evaluative studies, conducted on much larger scale and scope than the present study, have confirmed that both HPMHWDP and TSC/SBM, despite some initial shortcomings, have largely been successful in fulfilling the objectives they set-out to achieve. A mix of mass media campaign and interpersonal communication in an informal setting were found to be most effective in creating a high awareness. Also, an analysis of socio-economic variables, demonstrated that awareness about the project is closely associated with need for the services under the project, as was demonstrated in case of BPL respondents and respondents engaged in occupations involving self-initiative such as agriculture/horticulture, daily wagers and self-employed. There is an old quotation, “Advertisements don’t sell products, people do.” The statement is as true for community outreach as it is for advertising. In fact, the most effective communication with communities is not what they are told, but what they consider is in their larger interest, and brings about a collective action without outside intervention.

References :

- Asian Development Bank. (2010). Climate change adaptation plan: Sustainable strategies for water resources. Mandaluyong City, Philippines: Asian Development Bank.
- Bandura, A. (2008). Social cognitive theory of mass communication. In J. Bryant, & M. B. Oliver (Eds.), *Media effects: Advances in theory and research* (pp. 94-124). New York: Routledge.
- Batten, T. R. (1962). *Training for community development: A critical study of method*. London: Oxford University Press.
- Binswanger-Mkhize, H. P., Aiyar, S. S., Regt, J. P., Serrano-Berthet, R., Helling, L., Domelen, J. V., et al. (2010). Historical roots and evolution of community driven development. In H. P. Binswanger-Mkhize, J. P. Regt, & S. Spector (Eds.), *Local and community driven development: Moving to scale in theory and practice* (pp. 27-71). Washington, D.C.: The World Bank.
- Chambers, R. (1983). *Rural development: putting the last first*. Harlow: Longman Scientific and Technical.
- Chekki, D. A. (1979). A prolegomena to community development and planned change. In D. A. Chekki (Ed.), *Community development, theory and method of planned change* (pp. 3-24). New Delhi: Vikas Publishing House Pvt. Ltd.
- Dey, S. K. (1964). *Community Development*. New Delhi: Asia Publishing House.
- Dreze, J., & Sen, A. (2002). *India: Development and participation*. New Delhi: Oxford University Press.
- Freire, P. (1983). *Pedagogy of the oppressed*. New York: Continuum.
- Gandhi, M. (1942, July 26). *My idea of village swaraj*. Harijan.
- Gupta, H. K. (2006). *Joint forest management: Policy, participation and practices in India - with reference to the Northwest Himalayas*. New Delhi: International Book Distributors.
- Gupta, V. S. (1995). *Third revolution in Indian perspective: Contemporary issues and themes in communication*. New Delhi: Concept Publishing Company.
- IEG Review Team. (2018). *India - IN: Mid-Himalayan (HP) Watersheds (English)*. Washington, D.C.: World Bank Group. Retrieved from <http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/en/957951521102541772/India-IN-Mid-Himalayan-HP-Watersheds>.

- Institute of Development Studies. (n.d.). The CLTS approach. Retrieved May 10, 2019, from CommunityLedTotalSanitation.org: <https://www.communityledtotalsanitation.org/page/clts-approach>
- Kaufman, H. F. (1979). The activity field: A perspective for community development. In D. A. Chekki (Ed.), *Community Development: Theory and method of planned change* (pp. 76-89). New Delhi: Vikas Publishing House Pvt Ltd.
- Kurien, C. T. (1992). *Growth and justice: Aspects of India's development experience*. New Delhi: Oxford University Press.
- Mansuri, G., & Rao, V. (2004). *Community-based and -driven development*. World Bank Research Observer, 19 (1), 1-40.
- Mefalopulos, P. (2003, December). *Theory and practice of participatory communication: The case of the FAO project "Communication for Development in Southern Africa"*. Retrieved January 21, 2015, from University of Texas Libraries: <http://hdl.handle.net/2152/776>
- Meier, G. M. (1970). *Leading issues in economic development: Studies in international poverty*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Oommen, T. K. (1984). *Social transformation in rural India: Mobilisation and state intervention*. Ghaziabad: Vikas Publishing House Pvt. Ltd.
- Pathak, B. (1991). *Road to freedom: A sociological study on the abolition of scavenging in India*. New Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass Publishers.
- Planning Commission. (1951). *1st Five year plan*. (Planning Commission, Govt. of India) Retrieved April 24, 2019, from Planning Commission: <http://planningcommission.gov.in/plans/planrel/fiveyr/index1.html>
- Planning Commission. (1956). *2nd Five Year Plan*. (Planning Commission, Govt. of India) Retrieved May 8, 2019, from Planning Commission: <http://planningcommission.nic.in/plans/planrel/fiveyr/2nd/2pintro.htm>
- Planning Commission. (1954). *Building for tomorrow: First year of community projects*. New Delhi: Community Projects Administration (Planning Commission), Govt. of India.
- Planning Commission. (2013). *Evaluation study on Total Sanitation Campaign*. Retrieved May 10, 2019, from Planning Commission:

http://planningcommission.gov.in/reports/peoreport/peo/rep_tscv1_2205.pdf

- Radhakrishna, R., & Chandrasekhar, S. (2008). Overview: Growth: Achievements and distress. In R. Radhakrishna (Ed.), *India development report 2008*. New Delhi: Oxford University Press.
- Reddy, A. R. (2009). *Gandhi and globalisation*. New Delhi: Mittal Publications.
- Research and Reference Division. (1978). *India 1977-78: A reference annual*. New Delhi: Ministry of Information and Broadcasting, Publications Division, Govt. of India.
- Rogers, E. M. (1976). Communication and development: The passing of the dominant paradigm. *Communication Research*, 3 (2), 213-240.
- Sikka, S. K. (2010). *Mass media and contemporary social issues*. New Delhi: Cyber Tech Publications.
- Singh, S. P. (2000). *Sulabh sanitation movement: Vision-2000 plus* (2nd ed.). New Delhi: Sulabh International Social Service Organisation.
- Singhal, A., & Rogers, E. (1999). *Entertainment-education: A communication strategy for social change*. New York, London: Routledge.
- State Plan Division. (2003). *Himachal Pradesh Development Report*. New Delhi: Planning Commission, Government of India.
- Todaro, M. P., & Smith, S. C. (2003). *Economic Development*. New Delhi: Pearson Education Pvt. Ltd.
- UNDP. (1996). *Human development report 1996*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- United Nations Division for Sustainable Development Goals. (n.d.). *Sustainable Development Goals*. United Nations. <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/?menu=1300>. Retrieved May 7, 2019, from United Nations Sustainable Development Goals Knowledge Platform: <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/?menu=1300>
- World Bank. (2017). *Himachal Pradesh Mid-Himalayan Watershed Development Project*. The World Bank.
